

Review Article

Psychological Factors in Cardiovascular Disease: A Comprehensive Review of Mechanisms, Epidemiology, and Treatment Approaches

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ABSTRACT

Anxiety, depression, and stress are exceedingly common among patients with cardiovascular disease (CVD), and they significantly increase the risk of cardiac events, contributing to worse overall outcomes. There is compelling evidence linking these psychological factors to adverse cardiac events such as acute myocardial infarction (MI) and sudden cardiac death. This review seeks to explore the intersection of mental health and cardiovascular function, highlighting the physiological, behavioral, and psychological mechanisms that drive the increased risk and poorer prognosis in these patients.

INTRODUCTION

Cardiovascular disease (CVD) is one of the leading causes of morbidity and mortality in the world. Presence of several advanced medical treatment and preventive strategies there are no of patients who experience poor outcomes, including recurrent cardiac events, sudden cardiac death and bad quality of life. One of the very critical contributors for cardiac diseases are psychological factor such as depression, anxiety and stress¹. These mental health conditions are highly prevalent among CVD patients and have been shown to not only coexist with heart disease but also exacerbate its progression². A growing body of research suggests that psychological distress,

including anxiety and depression, should be considered integral risk factors for CVD, warranting as much attention as more traditionally recognized risk factors such as hypertension and hyperlipidaemia³. According to estimates by the World Health Organization, cardiovascular system disorders claim nearly 18 million lives each year, accounting for over 30% of global deaths. Further, their risk of occurrence is governed significantly by such behavioral factors as tobacco use, excessive alcohol consumption, an unhealthy diet and inadequate physical activity. This risk also traces back to physiological factors, including high blood pressure and high blood cholesterol and glucose levels, which are linked to

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underlying social factors, including aging, income and urbanization⁴.

Pathogenesis and Mechanisms Linking Depression, Anxiety, and CVD

Psychological Mechanisms

Heart disease outcomes experience significant impact from depression and anxiety because these mental conditions modify how patients behave and live their lives. Depressed patients often struggle to follow medical instructions which causes them to follow treatment plans less consistently and fail to adhere to prescribed medications and dietary and exercise recommendations. Heart failure (HF) and coronary artery disease (CAD) patients demonstrate worse clinical results when they fail to follow their medical treatment plans.^{1,5} The chronic form of anxiety causes stress-induced myocardial ischemia which helps develop or worsen CAD. Research indicates that mental stress elevates catecholamine levels which results in elevated platelet aggregation together with vasoconstriction and increased risk of atherosclerotic plaque rupture.¹ Although psychosocial stresses have been reviewed here as individual entities, generally, these stresses tend to cluster together. When they do so, risk ratios for cardiac events often rise substantially. For example, in one study of post-MI patients, the presence of high levels of life stress and social isolation were each associated with an ≈ 2 -fold increase in subsequent events. but when the 2 factors occurred together, the rate of subsequent events was 4-fold higher. A similar synergy between these 2 factors has also been reported among healthy individuals⁶

Biological Mechanisms

Autonomic Nervous System (ANS) Dysregulation: The autonomic nervous system shows an imbalance when people experience long-term psychological stress because sympathetic activation rises while parasympathetic control

reduces. The mismatch between nervous system activities leads to endothelial dysfunction and platelet activation as well as an inflammatory state that increase cardiovascular risks.⁷

Platelet Activation: Research indicates that platelet activation serves as a possible connection between depression and CVD development. Platelets serve two essential functions in the body by helping blood coagulation and facilitating inflammatory responses and maintaining vascular health. Depressed patients who experience platelet function dysregulation face increased risks of both MI and stroke because of thrombosis and atherosclerosis progression.³

Oxidative Stress and Inflammation: Depression has been associated with increased levels of inflammatory markers such as C-reactive protein (CRP) and interleukin-6 (IL-6). These markers contribute to endothelial dysfunction and a pro-thrombotic state, thus heightening the risk of cardiovascular events. Furthermore, depression and anxiety are linked to mitochondrial dysfunction, which may impair the body's ability to regulate cardiovascular responses to stress.⁸

Behavioral Factors

Psychological distress can influence health behaviors in detrimental ways. Depressed and anxious individuals may engage in unhealthy coping mechanisms such as smoking, poor dietary habits, and sedentary lifestyles. These behaviors further contribute to cardiovascular risk and can worsen the overall prognosis in CVD patients. In addition, mental health disorders are associated with poorer medication adherence, which has been recognized as a key factor influencing clinical outcomes in CVD patients. Studies have shown that non-adherence to prescribed medications, including those for heart failure or hypertension, is higher in patients suffering from depression and anxiety.¹

Epidemiology and Clinical Outcomes

Prevalence of Depression and Anxiety in CVD

Research shows that depression and anxiety affect 40% of heart failure patients and 20-30% of those with coronary artery disease. Patients with these conditions face a higher risk of hospital admissions and cardiac event recurrence along with increased mortality rates. Depression and anxiety in CVD patients cause negative impacts on their health-related quality of life which leads to reduced survival rates and accelerated functional decline. Heart failure patients who experience depression demonstrate reduced quality of life while experiencing more disabilities and requiring more hospital admissions.^{1,9}

Impact on Cardiac Events and Mortality

Studies show a causal relationship between cardiac events and depression. A causal relationship exists between depression and adverse cardiac events. Patients with depression are at a higher risk for incidents such as acute myocardial infarction (AMI), sudden cardiac death, and recurrent coronary events. The presence of anxiety disorders, such as generalized anxiety disorder (GAD), post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), and panic disorder, further exacerbates this risk. Studies have demonstrated that individuals with depression are twice as likely to develop myocardial infarction compared to the general population. Additionally, depression has been associated with a 30–87% increased risk of ischemic heart disease (IHD) events and a significant rise in fatal and non-fatal strokes.^{1,8}

Impact of Psychological Factors on Heart Failure

Psychological factors, especially depression and anxiety, have been shown to have a particularly detrimental effect on patients with heart failure. These patients are more likely to experience negative outcomes, including hospitalizations and death. Depression, in particular, has been found to be a strong predictor of poor prognosis in heart

failure patients, independent of other cardiovascular risk factors. The high prevalence of frailty in heart failure patients, especially those who are depressed, further complicates the management of this population. Frail patients with depression are at a significantly increased risk for poor functional outcomes, including disability, readmission, and mortality.³

Treatment Approaches for Depression and Anxiety in CVD

Pharmacological Treatment

1. Selective Serotonin Reuptake Inhibitors (SSRIs): SSRIs are commonly prescribed to treat depression in patients with cardiovascular disease. Evidence suggests that SSRIs are generally safe in these patients and may offer some cardiac benefit, especially in those with coronary artery disease. However, their effectiveness in heart failure patients remains less clear.⁶

2. Other Antidepressants: Other classes of antidepressants, such as serotonin-norepinephrine reuptake inhibitors (SNRIs), may be considered for patients with CVD, although more research is needed to determine their overall benefit and safety.¹⁰

Psychotherapy

Studies demonstrate that psychotherapy specifically using cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT) effectively treats depression among patients who have CAD and heart failure. The effectiveness of psychotherapy for emotional regulation and stress reduction and cardiovascular treatment adherence exists despite limited research showing its direct cardiac advantages. Future research must investigate how psychotherapy affects heart disease results.⁹

Cardiac Rehabilitation

Cardiac rehabilitation plays a crucial role in improving outcomes for CVD patients, especially those with depression and anxiety. A comprehensive rehabilitation program that includes physical exercise, education on managing psychological stress, and emotional support can help patients improve their overall health and well-being. Cardiac rehabilitation programs that incorporate psychological counseling may be particularly beneficial in reducing the burden of mental health symptoms in these patients.⁵

CONCLUSION

Anxiety, depression, and stress are significant risk factors for cardiovascular disease and have a profound impact on clinical outcomes. These psychological conditions influence both the physiological and behavioral aspects of CVD, contributing to worse prognosis, poor quality of life, and increased mortality. It is critical that depression and anxiety be recognized and managed as part of the overall treatment strategy for CVD patients. Effective pharmacological treatments, psychotherapy, and cardiac rehabilitation programs can help mitigate the adverse effects of these conditions and improve the overall health of patients with heart disease. Further research is needed to better understand the complex interplay between mental health and cardiovascular disease, to develop more targeted and effective treatment strategies that address both the psychological and cardiovascular aspects of patient care.

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REFERENCES

1. Silverman, A. L., Herzog, A. A., & Silverman, D. I. (2019). Hearts and minds: Stress, anxiety, and depression: Unsung risk factors

for cardiovascular disease. *Cardiology in Review*, 27(4), 202–207. <https://doi.org/10.1097/crd.0000000000000228>

2. Celano, C. M., Villegas, A. C., Albanese, A. M., Gaggin, H. K., & Huffman, J. C. (2018). Depression and anxiety in heart failure: A review. *Harvard Review of Psychiatry*, 26(4), 175–184. <https://doi.org/10.1097/HRP.000000000000162>
3. Amadio, P., Zarà, M., Sandrini, L., Ieraci, A., & Barbieri, S. S. (2020). Depression and cardiovascular disease: The viewpoint of platelets. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 21(20), 7560. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms21207560>
4. Carola, V., Vincenzo, C., Di Vincenzo, G., Morale, C., Cecchi, V., & Nicolais, G. (2024). Psychological risk factors and cardiovascular disease. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 15, 1419731. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2024.1419731>
5. Chauvet-Gelinier J-C, Bonin B. Stress, anxiety and depression in heart disease patients: A major challenge for cardiac rehabilitation. *Ann Phys Rehabil Med* (2016), <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.rehab.2016.09.002>
6. Rozanski, A., Blumenthal, J. A., & Kaplan, J. (1999). Impact of psychological factors on the pathogenesis of cardiovascular disease and implications for therapy. *Circulation*, 99(16), 2192–2217. <https://doi.org/10.1161/01.cir.99.16.2192>
7. Bordoni, B., Marelli, F., Morabito, B., & Sacconi, B. (2018). Depression and anxiety in patients with chronic heart failure. *Future Cardiology*, 14(2), 115–119. <https://doi.org/10.2217/fca-2017-0073>
8. Jiang, W. (2020). Depression and cardiovascular disorders in the elderly. *Clinics in Geriatric Medicine*, 36(2), 211–219. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cger.2019.11.003>

9. Zambrano, J., Celano, C. M., Januzzi, J. L., Massey, C. N., Chung, W.-J., Millstein, R. A., & Huffman, J. C. (2020). Psychiatric and psychological interventions for depression in patients with heart disease: A scoping review. *Journal of the American Heart Association*, 9(22), e018686. <https://doi.org/10.1161/JAHA.120.018686>
10. Zhang, Y., Chen, Y., & Ma, L. (2018). Depression and cardiovascular disease in elderly: Current understanding. *Journal of Clinical Neuroscience: Official Journal of the Neurosurgical Society of Australasia*, 47, 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jocn.2017.09.022>

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